

Logs In, Patches Out: Automated Vulnerability Repair via Tree-of-Thought LLM Analysis (Supplementary Material)

A Manual Validation

A.1 Correct (Developer-Matched)

In the developer patch for CVE-2016-5321 shown in Figure 1a, the condition of the `for` loop was changed. In contrast, the GPT-4o patch in Figure 1b added a conditional statement after the loop to achieve the same effect. We considered such functionally equivalent patches as correct and labelled as *Correct (developer-matched)*.

```
diff --git a/tools/tiffcrop.c b/tools/tiffcrop.c
--- a/tools/tiffcrop.c
+++ b/tools/tiffcrop.c
@@ -989,7 +989,7 @@ static int readSeparateTilesIntoBuffer (TIFF* in, uint8 *obuf,
     nrow = (row + tl > imagelength) ? imagelength - row : tl;
     for (col = 0; col < imagewidth; col += tw)
     {
-        for (s = 0; s < spp; s++)
+        for (s = 0; s < spp && (s < MAX_SAMPLES); s++)
         { /* Read each plane of a tile set into srcbufs[s] */
             tbytes = TIFFReadTile(in, srcbufs[s], col, row, 0, s);
             if (tbytes < 0 && !ignore)
```

(a) Developer's patch.

```
diff --git a/tools/tiffcrop.c b/tools/tiffcrop.c
--- a/tools/tiffcrop.c
+++ b/tools/tiffcrop.c
@@ -991,6 +991,7 @@ static int readSeparateTilesIntoBuffer (TIFF* in, uint8 *obuf,
     {
         for (s = 0; s < spp; s++)
         { /* Read each plane of a tile set into srcbufs[s] */
+            if (s < 0 || s >= MAX_SAMPLES) continue; // Ensure 's' is within bounds
             tbytes = TIFFReadTile(in, srcbufs[s], col, row, 0, s);
             if (tbytes < 0 && !ignore)
         }
```

(b) GPT-4o's patch.

Figure 1: (Top) Developer's patch; (Bottom) GPT-4o's patch for CVE-2016-5321.

A.2 Correct (Alternative)

Figure 2a shows the developer patch for bugzilla-2611. Figure 2b presents the patch generated by GPT-4o, which modifies a function different from the one changed in the developer patch. However, the crash location in the sanitizer log (Figure 2c) is in the `OJPEGDecodeRaw` function of `tif_jpeg.c`, and GPT-4o correctly identified this line as the source of the divide-by-zero vulnerability. As a result, GPT-4o patched the bug by adding a conditional statement to check if the denominator, `sp->bytes_per_line`, is zero. We classified this patch as alternative correct. In such cases, where the LLM patch addresses the bug correctly even if it is not semantically identical to the developer patch, we labeled the result as *Correct (alternative)*.

```
diff --git a/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c b/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c
--- a/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c
+++ b/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c
@@ -244,6 +244,7 @@ typedef enum {
    typedef struct {
        TIFF* tif;
+       int decoder_ok;
        #ifndef LIBJPEG_ENCAP_EXTERNAL
        JMP_BUF exit_jmpbuf;
        #endif
@@ -722,6 +723,7 @@ OJPEGPreDecode(TIFF* tif, uint16
    }
    sp->write_curstrile++;
+   sp->decoder_ok = 1;
    return(1);
}

@@ -784,8 +786,14 @@ OJPEGPreDecodeSkipScanlines(TIFF
    * tif)
    static int
    OJPEGDecode(TIFF* tif, uint8* buf, tmsize_t cc,
                uint16 s)
    {
+   static const char module[]="OJPEGDecode";
    OJPEGState* sp=(OJPEGState*)tif->tif_data;
    (void)s;
+   if (!sp->decoder_ok) {
+       TIFFErrorExt(tif->tif_clientdata,module,
+                   "Cannot decode: decoder not
+                   correctly initialized");
+       return 0;
+   }
    if (sp->libjpeg_jpeg_query_style==0) {
        if (OJPEGDecodeRaw(tif,buf,cc)==0)
```

(a) Developer's patch.

```
diff --git a/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c b/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c
--- a/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c
+++ b/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c
@@ -811,8 +811,14 @@ OJPEGDecodeRaw(TIFF* tif, uint8*
    buf, tmsize_t cc)
    uint8* ocr;
    uint8* p;
    uint32 q;
-   uint8* r;
+   // FIXME: Crash CWE-369: Divide By Zero
+   uint8* r;
    uint8 sx,sy;
+   if (sp->bytes_per_line == 0) {
+       TIFFErrorExt(tif->tif_clientdata,module,
+                   "Bytes per line is zero");
+       return(0);
+   }
    if (cc % sp->bytes_per_line != 0) {
        TIFFErrorExt(tif->tif_clientdata,
                    module,
                    "Fractional scanline not
                    read");
```

(b) GPT-4o's patch.

```
==890926==ERROR: AddressSanitizer: FPE on unknown address
0x55cae42649d5 (pc 0x55cae42649d5 bp 0x7ffe9f7a45a0 sp 0
x7ffe9f7a4520 T0)
#0 0x55cae42649d4 in OJPEGDecodeRaw src/libtiff/
tif_jpeg.c:816
#1 0x55cae4264885 in OJPEGDecode src/libtiff/
tif_jpeg.c:791
#2 0x55cae41d4bee in TIFFReadScanline src/libtiff/
tif_read.c:304
#3 0x55cae417b750 in quant src/tools/tiffmedian.c:771
#4 0x55cae4173304 in main src/tools/tiffmedian.c:283
#5 0x7f6ba749dc86 in __libc_start_main (/lib/x86_64-
linux-gnu/libc.so.6+0x21c86)
#6 0x55cae4171539 in _start (tiffmedian+0x171539)

SUMMARY: AddressSanitizer: FPE src/libtiff/tif_jpeg.c
:816 in OJPEGDecodeRaw
```

(c) AddressSanitizer log.

Figure 2: (Left) Developer's patch; (Right, top) GPT-4o's patch; (Right, bottom) AddressSanitizer log for bugzilla-2611.

A.3 Incorrect (Failed Some Test Cases)

Figure 3a shows the developer patch for CVE-2017-6965, where a conditional check was added before executing the `byte_put` function to prevent buffer overflow by ensuring the buffer size is not exceeded. Figure 3b presents the patch generated by GPT-4o, which adds the condition `if (reloc->r_offset + size <= 157)` to address the buffer overflow vulnerability. Figure 3c provides the sanitizer log that triggers CVE-2017-6965, showing that the overflow occurred in a buffer of size 157 bytes. GPT-4o referred to the sanitizer log and inserted a check that compares against the buffer size, but this patch only prevents a specific PoC and is not general. In such cases, where the patch succeeds by using a specific number rather than applying a general fix, we classified the result as incorrect and labelled it as *Incorrect (failed some test cases)*.

```
diff --git a/binutils/readelf.c b/binutils/readelf.c
--- a/binutils/readelf.c
+++ b/binutils/readelf.c
@@ -11591,6 +11591,7 @@ process_syminfo (FILE * file
    ATTRIBUTE_UNUSED)
    static bfd_boolean
    target_specific_reloc_handling (Elf_Internal_Rela *
        reloc, unsigned char * start,
+   unsigned char * end,
    Elf_Internal_Sym * symtab)
    {
    ... (Omitted)
@@ -11631,13 +11632,19 @@
    target_specific_reloc_handling (Elf_Internal_Rela *
        reloc,
        handle_sym_diff:
            if (saved_sym != NULL)
            {
+   int reloc_size = reloc_type == 1 ? 4 : 2;
    ... (Omitted)
-   byte_put (start + reloc->r_offset, value, reloc_type
+   == 1 ? 4 : 2);
+   if (start + reloc->r_offset + reloc_size >= end)
+   /* PR 21137 */
+   error (... (Omitted), start + reloc->r_offset +
+   reloc_size, end);
+   else
+   byte_put (start + reloc->r_offset, value,
+   reloc_size);
    ... (Omitted)
    case 2: /* R_MN10300_16 */
        if (saved_sym != NULL)
        {
+   int reloc_size = reloc_type == 1 ? 4 : 2;
    ... (Omitted)
    case 0x43: /* R_RL78_ABS16. */
-   byte_put (start + reloc->r_offset, value, 2);
+   if (start + reloc->r_offset + 2 >= end)
+   error (... (Omitted), start + reloc->r_offset + 2,
+   end);
+   else
+   byte_put (start + reloc->r_offset, value, 2);
        value = 0;
        return TRUE;
@@ -12340,7 +12360,7 @@ apply_relocations (void *
        file,
        reloc_type = get_reloc_type (rp->r_info);
-   if (target_specific_reloc_handling (rp, start,
+   symtab))
+   if (target_specific_reloc_handling (rp, start, end,
+   symtab))
    ... (Omitted)
```

(a) Developer's patch.

```
diff --git a/binutils/readelf.c b/binutils/readelf.c
--- a/binutils/readelf.c
+++ b/binutils/readelf.c
@@ -11603,52 +11603,56 @@
    target_specific_reloc_handling (
    Elf_Internal_Rela * reloc,
    static Elf_Internal_Sym * saved_sym = NULL;

    switch (reloc_type)
    ... (Omitted)
-   byte_put (start + reloc->r_offset, value,
+   reloc_type == 1 ? 4 : 2);
+   size_t size = (reloc_type == 1 ? 4 : 2);
+   if (reloc->r_offset + size <= 157) {
+   byte_put (start + reloc->r_offset, value, size);
+   }
    ... (Omitted)
```

(b) GPT-4o's patch.

```
==127459==ERROR: AddressSanitizer: heap-buffer-overflow
on address 0x60e0000000ec at pc 0x55cbb840c098 bp 0
x7ffc277e21b0 sp 0x7ffc277e21a0
... (Omitted)
0x60e0000000ec is located 15 bytes to the right of 157-byte
region [0x60e000000040,0x60e0000000dd)
allocated by thread T0 here:
#0 0x7fc4a5546b40 in __interceptor_malloc (/usr/lib/
x86_64-linux-gnu/libasan.so.4+0xdeb40)
#1 0x55cbb8369191 in get_data src/binutils/readelf.c
:393
#2 0x55cbb83b5f7c in load_specific_debug_section src/
binutils/readelf.c:12829
#3 0x55cbb83b7bb2 in display_debug_section src/binutils
/readelf.c:13009
#4 0x55cbb83b829c in process_section_contents src/
binutils/readelf.c:13091
#5 0x55cbb83ccef0 in process_object src/binutils/
readelf.c:16780
#6 0x55cbb83cea02 in process_file src/binutils/readelf.
c:17154
#7 0x7fc4a4377c86 in __libc_start_main (/lib/x86_64-
linux-gnu/libc.so.6+0x21c86)
SUMMARY: AddressSanitizer: heap-buffer-overflow src/
binutils/elfcomm.c:75 in byte_put_little_endian
```

(c) AddressSanitizer log.

Figure 3: (Left) Developer's patch; (Right, top) GPT-4o's patch; (Right, bottom) AddressSanitizer log for CVE-2017-6965.

A.4 Incorrect (Failed All Test Cases)

Figure 4 shows that GPT-3.5-turbo attempted to patch CVE-2017-5975 by removing the entire `zzip_mem_entry_new` function. Although this prevented the vulnerability, we considered it failed due to altered functionality. The project version containing CVE-2017-5975 did not include any unit tests, so no functional tests were available. In such cases, as well as in cases where the patch obviously alters functionality or produces abnormal results, we classified the patch as incorrect and labeled it as *Incorrect (failed all test cases)*.

```
diff --git a/zzip/memdisk.c b/zzip/memdisk.c
--- a/zzip/memdisk.c
+++ b/zzip/memdisk.c
@@ -163,85 +163,7 @@ zzip_mem_disk_load(ZZIP_MEM_DISK * dir, ZZIP_DISK * disk)
 * right into the diskdir_entry for later usage in higher layers.
 * returns: new item, or null on error (setting errno = ENOMEM|EBADMSG)
 */
- zzip__new__ ZZIP_MEM_ENTRY *
- zzip_mem_entry_new(ZZIP_DISK * disk, ZZIP_DISK_ENTRY * entry)
- {
-     if (! disk || ! entry)
- ... (Omitted)
-     return item;
-     ____;
- error:
-     zzip_mem_entry_free(item);
-     return 0;
-     ____;
- }
+     free(item->zz_data);
 /* find an extra block for the given datatype code.
```

Figure 4: GPT-3.5-turbo’s patch to address CVE-2017-5975.

B Failure Case Analysis

B.1 Model-Agnostic Failure Cases

CVE-2016-8691 Figure 5a shows the developer patch for CVE-2016-8691, where the vulnerability was addressed by adding checks for `siz->comps[i].hsamp` and `siz->comps[i].vsamp` to prevent a divide-by-zero error. Figure 5b presents an example of a patch generated by GPT-4o. By analyzing the sanitizer log (Figure 5c), GPT-4o identified the divide-by-zero vulnerability and modified line 1195 of `jpc_dec.c`. At this line, where the `JPC_CEILDIV` function is called, GPT-4o attempted to patch the issue by checking the denominator variables `siz->comps[compno].hsamp` and `siz->comps[compno].vsamp` for zero values.

```
diff --git a/src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_cs.c b/src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_cs.c
--- a/src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_cs.c
+++ b/src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_cs.c
@@ -512,6 +512,16 @@ static int jpc_siz_getparms(
     jpc_ms_t *ms, jpc_cstate_t *cstate,
         jas_free(siz->comps);
     return -1;
 }
+ if (siz->comps[i].hsamp == 0 || siz->comps[i].
+     hsamp > 255) {
+     jas_eprintf("invalid XRsiz value %d\n", siz->
+     comps[i].hsamp);
+     jas_free(siz->comps);
+     return -1;
+ }
+ if (siz->comps[i].vsamp == 0 || siz->comps[i].
+     vsamp > 255) {
+     jas_eprintf("invalid YRsiz value %d\n", siz->
+     comps[i].vsamp);
+     jas_free(siz->comps);
+     return -1;
+ }
     siz->comps[i].sgnd = (tmp >> 7) & 1;
     siz->comps[i].prec = (tmp & 0x7f) + 1;
 }
```

(a) Developer's patch.

```
diff --git a/src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_dec.c b/src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_dec.c
--- a/src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_dec.c
+++ b/src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_dec.c
@@ -1189,12 +1189,23 @@ static int
     jpc_dec_process_siz(jpc_dec_t *dec, jpc_ms_t *ms
 )
     ++cmpt) {
     cmpt->prec = siz->comps[compno].prec;
     cmpt->sgnd = siz->comps[compno].sgnd;
+// FIXME: Crash CWE-369: Divide By Zero
     cmpt->hstep = siz->comps[compno].hsamp;
     cmpt->vstep = siz->comps[compno].vsamp;
-    cmpt->width = JPC_CEILDIV(dec->xend, cmpt->hstep)
-    -
-    JPC_CEILDIV(dec->xstart, cmpt->hstep);
-    cmpt->height = JPC_CEILDIV(dec->yend, cmpt->
+    vstep) -
+    JPC_CEILDIV(dec->ystart, cmpt->vstep);
+    if (cmpt->hstep > 0) {
+    cmpt->width = JPC_CEILDIV(dec->xend, cmpt->hstep)
+    -
+    JPC_CEILDIV(dec->xstart, cmpt->hstep);
+    } else {
+    cmpt->width = JPC_CEILDIV(dec->xend, 1) -
+    JPC_CEILDIV(dec->xstart, 1);
+    }
+    if (cmpt->vstep > 0) {
+    cmpt->height = JPC_CEILDIV(dec->yend, cmpt->
+    vstep) -
+    JPC_CEILDIV(dec->ystart, cmpt->vstep);
+    } else {
+    cmpt->height = JPC_CEILDIV(dec->yend, 1) -
+    JPC_CEILDIV(dec->ystart, 1);
+    }
     cmpt->hsubstep = 0;
     cmpt->vsubstep = 0;
 }
```

(b) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch.

```
jpc_dec.c:1195:5: runtime error: division by zero
#0 0x5650daf2f01a in jpc_dec_process_siz src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_dec.c:1195
#1 0x5650daf256a9 in jpc_dec_decode src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_dec.c:390
#2 0x5650daf24d05 in jpc_decode src/libjasper/jpc/jpc_dec.c:254
#3 0x5650daef53a7 in jas_image_decode src/libjasper/base/jas_image.c:372
#4 0x5650daef2c9b in main src/appl/iminfo.c:179
#5 0x7ff5aab4dc86 in __libc_start_main (/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libc.so.6+0x21c86)
#6 0x5650daef29d9 in _start (src/appl/iminfo+0xf29d9)
```

(c) UndefinedBehaviorSanitizer log.

Figure 5: (Left) Developer's patch; (Right, top) GPT-4o's patch; (Right, bottom) UndefinedBehaviorSanitizer log for CVE-2016-8691.

However, after applying the patch, running the PoC again resulted in the same divide-by-zero error, as shown in Figure 6a. The new error occurs at a different location from the original divide-by-zero, as illustrated in Figure 6b. At this location, the JPC_CEILDIV function also divides by `siz->comps[compno].hsamp` (where `cmpt->hstep` equals `siz->comps[compno].hsamp`; see Figure 5b)). Because the location in the sanitizer log indicates the line where the bug is triggered, not the root cause, no LLM was able to generate a correct patch without addressing additional code locations.

```

jpc_dec.c:1250:20: runtime error: division by zero
#0 0x55e683b3017a in jpc_dec_process_siz src/
libjasper/jpc/jpc_dec.c:1250
#1 0x55e683b25829 in jpc_dec_decode src/libjasper/jpc/
jpc_dec.c:390
#2 0x55e683b24e85 in jpc_decode src/libjasper/jpc/
jpc_dec.c:254
#3 0x55e683af5527 in jas_image_decode src/libjasper/
base/jas_image.c:372
#4 0x55e683af2e1b in main src/appl/imaginfo.c:179
#5 0x7f571a2dbc86 in __libc_start_main (/lib/x86_64-
linux-gnu/libc.so.6+0x21c86)
#6 0x55e683af2b59 in _start (src/appl/imaginfo+0xf2b59
)

```

(a) UndefinedBehaviorSanitizer log of CVE-2016-8691 after applying the patch generated by GPT-4o.

```

1246 for (compno = 0, cmpt = dec->cmpts, tcomp =
      tile->tcomps;
1247      compno < dec->numcomps; ++compno, ++cmpt,
      ++tcomp) {
1248     tcomp->rlvls = 0;
1249     tcomp->data = 0;
1250     tcomp->xstart = JPC_CEILDIV(tile->xstart,
      cmpt->hstep);
1251     tcomp->ystart = JPC_CEILDIV(tile->ystart,
      cmpt->vstep);
1252     tcomp->xend = JPC_CEILDIV(tile->xend,
      cmpt->hstep);
1253     tcomp->yend = JPC_CEILDIV(tile->yend,
      cmpt->vstep);
1254     tcomp->tsfb = 0;
1255 }

```

(b) Code snippet of crash location after applying the GPT-4o's patch.

Figure 6: (Left) UndefinedBehaviorSanitizer error log after the GPT-4o patch; (Right) corresponding code location that still triggers the sanitizer.

Use-After-Free CVE-2018-8806 and CVE-2018-8964 are Use-After-Free (UAF) vulnerabilities. UAF bugs are typically mitigated by modifying both the location where the pointer is freed and where it is subsequently reused, or by patching the more fundamental root cause. However, LLMs more frequently attempted to fix only one of these locations rather than both, and often failed to address the root cause of the UAF vulnerability. Figures 7a, 7b, 8a and 8b show examples of such cases.

```
diff --git a/util/decompile.c b/util/decompile.c
--- a/util/decompile.c
+++ b/util/decompile.c
@@ -344,6 +344,7 @@ getString(struct
     SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM *act)
     case PUSH_INT: /* INTEGER */
         t=malloc(10); /* 32-bit decimal */
         sprintf(t,"%ld", act->p.Integer );
+         act->p.String = NULL; // Safety:
+         Nullify pointer immediately to prevent use-after
+         -free
         return t;
... (Omitted)
@@ -352,7 +353,7 @@ getString(struct
     SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM *act)
         strcat(t,"");
         return t;
     case PUSH_CONSTANT16: /* CONSTANT16 */
-         t=malloc(strlen(pool[act->p.
+         Constant16])+3); /* 2 '\''s and a NULL */
+         t=malloc(strlen(pool[act->p.
+         Constant16])+3); /* 2 '\''s and a NULL */
         strcpy(t,"");
         strcat(t,pool[act->p.Constant16]);
         strcat(t,"");
```

(a) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch (1).

```
diff --git a/util/parser.c b/util/parser.c
--- a/util/parser.c
+++ b/util/parser.c
@@ -1003,11 +1003,16 @@ parseSWF_ACTIONRECORD(FILE *
     f, int *thisactionp, SWF_ACTION *actions)
     break;
     default:
         printf("Unknown data type to push %x\n", param->
             Type );
         exit(1);
     }
-   act->Params = (struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM *)
-       realloc (act->Params,
-       (act->NumParam + 1) *
-       sizeof (struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM));
+   struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM *newParams;
+   newParams = realloc (act->Params, (act->NumParam +
+       1) * sizeof (struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM));
+   if (!newParams) {
+       free(act->Params);
+       perror("Memory reallocation failed");
+       exit(1);
+   }
+   act->Params = newParams;
+   }
    break;
```

(b) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch (2).

Figure 7: (Left) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch to address CVE-2018-8806 (1); (Right) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch to address CVE-2018-8806 (2).

```
diff --git a/util/decompile.c b/util/decompile.c
--- a/util/decompile.c
+++ b/util/decompile.c
@@ -387,13 +387,18 @@ getName(struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM *act)
     if(strlen(t)) /* Not a zero length string */
         return t;
     else
+     {
+         free(t); /* Explicit free to prevent memory leak */
+         t=NULL;
+         return "this";
+     }
     #if 0
... (Omitted)
@@ -401,7 +406,9 @@ getName(struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM *act)
     return t;
     else
     {
-         t=realloc(t,6);
+         free(t);
+         t=NULL;
+         t=malloc(6);
         return strcpy(t,"this");
     }
     case PUSH_CONSTANT16: /* CONSTANT16 */
@@ -411,7 +418,9 @@ getName(struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM *act)
     return t;
     else
     {
-         t=realloc(t,6);
+         free(t);
+         t=NULL;
+         t=malloc(6);
```

(a) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch (1).

```
diff --git a/util/parser.c b/util/parser.c
--- a/util/parser.c
+++ b/util/parser.c
@@ -1003,11 +1003,11 @@ parseSWF_ACTIONRECORD(FILE *
     f, int *thisactionp, SWF_ACTION *actions)
     break;
     default:
         printf("Unknown data type to push %x\n",
             param->Type );
     }
-   act->Params = (struct
-       SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM *) realloc (act->
-       Params,
-       (act->NumParam + 1) *
-       sizeof (struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM));
+   struct SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM * temp =
+       realloc (act->Params, (act->NumParam
+       + 1) * sizeof (struct
+       SWF_ACTIONPUSHPARAM));
+   if(temp == NULL) exit(1);
+   act->Params = temp;
+   }
    break;
+   }
    case SWFACTION_LOGICALNOT:
```

(b) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch (2).

Figure 8: (Left) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch to address CVE-2018-8964 (1); (Right) GPT-4o's unsuccessful patch to address CVE-2018-8964 (2).

CVE-2018-19664 Figure 9a shows the developer patch for CVE-2018-19664, where the condition for assigning the `put_pixel_rows` function pointer was modified. Figure 9b presents an example of an unsuccessful patch generated by GPT-4o, and Figure 9c displays a sanitizer log from a location different from where the developer made the fix.

When *Where-To-Fix* suggests line 550 of the `wrbmp.c` file, as indicated in the sanitizer log, this location is close to the actual faulty code and provides a valid code context. However, GPT-4o modifies only the part that superficially appears vulnerable to buffer overflow, rather than addressing the actual root cause related to the function pointer.

Figure 9: (Left) Developer's patch; (Right, top) GPT-4o's patch; (Right, bottom) AddressSanitizer log for CVE-2018-19664.

CVE-2013-7437 The CVE-2013-7437 vulnerability is an integer overflow (IO) bug that can lead to a buffer overflow (BO) when processing the large BMP image. Figure 10a shows the developer patch, where a conditional check is added to verify that the values of `bmpinfo.w` and `bmpinfo.h` do not exceed the integer range. Figure 10b presents a patch generated by GPT-4o, where the model creates a variable with an arbitrarily large value, such as 10,000,000, and adds a condition based on this value.

Figure 10c displays the original AddressSanitizer log of CVE-2013-7437, which reports the vulnerability as a heap-buffer-overflow. As a result, GPT-4o interpreted the issue as a BO vulnerability based on the log in Figure 10c, and added a conditional check for the arguments of the `bmp_readint` function near the bug location. However, since the root cause of this vulnerability is an integer overflow, GPT-4o could not patch the actual root cause. Figure 10d shows an UndefinedBehaviorSanitizer log generated with a different compile option, where the vulnerability is reported as an IO rather than a BO. This demonstrates that the type of sanitizer output can affect patch generation performance.

```
diff --git a/src/bitmap_io.c b/src/
bitmap_io.c
--- src/bitmap_io.c
+++ src/bitmap_io.c
@@ -478,12 +478,18 @@
     TRY(bmp_readint(f, 4, &bmpinfo.
        BlueMask));
     TRY(bmp_readint(f, 4, &bmpinfo.
        AlphaMask));
 }
- if ((signed int)bmpinfo.h < 0) {
-     bmpinfo.h = -bmpinfo.h;
+ if (bmpinfo.w > 0x7fffffff) {
+     goto format_error;
+ }
+ if (bmpinfo.h > 0x7fffffff) {
+     bmpinfo.h = (-bmpinfo.h) & 0
+ xfffffff;
+     bmpinfo.topdown = 1;
+ } else {
+     bmpinfo.topdown = 0;
+ }
+ if (bmpinfo.h > 0x7fffffff) {
+     goto format_error;
+ }
} else if (bmpinfo.InfoSize == 12) {
    /* old OS/2 format */
    bmpinfo.ctbits = 24; /* sample size
        in color table */
@@ -517,7 +523,7 @@

    /* color table, present only if bmpinfo
        .bits <= 8. */
    if (bmpinfo.bits <= 8) {
-     coltable = (int *) malloc(bmpinfo.
+     coltable = (int *) calloc(bmpinfo.
        ncolors * sizeof(int));
+     coltable = (int *) calloc(bmpinfo.
        ncolors, sizeof(int));
        if (!coltable) {
            goto std_error;
        }
    }
}

```

(a) Developer's patch.

```
diff --git a/src/bitmap_io.c b/src/bitmap_io.c
index 6cfeeb1..c23e0e6 100644
--- a/src/bitmap_io.c
+++ a/src/bitmap_io.c
@@ -597,28 +597,31 @@ static int bmp_readbody_bmp(FILE *f, double
    threshold, potrace_bitmap_t **bmp) {
    TRY(bmp_pad(f));
    }
    break;
- }
- case 0x010: /* 16-bit encoding */
+ case 0x010: /* 16-bit encoding */
    /* can't do this format because it is not well-documented and
        I
        don't have any samples */
    bmp_read_error = "cannot handle bmp 16-bit coding";
    goto format_error;
    break;
- case 0x018: /* 24-bit encoding */
+ case 0x018: /* 24-bit encoding */
+ case 0x020: /* 32-bit encoding */
    for (y=0; y<bmpinfo.h; y++) {
        bmp_pad_reset();
        for (x=0; x<bmpinfo.w; x++) {
-         TRY_EOF(bmp_readint(f, bmpinfo.bits/8, &c));
-         c = ((c>>16) & 0xff) + ((c>>8) & 0xff) + (c & 0xff);
+         #define BMP_MAX_SIZE 1000000 // Define a reasonable max size
+         if (bmpinfo.w * bmpinfo.h * (bmpinfo.bits/8) <= BMP_MAX_SIZE)
+             {
+                 TRY_EOF(bmp_readint(f, bmpinfo.bits/8, &c));
+             } else {
+                 bmp_read_error = "image dimensions too large";
+                 goto format_error;
+             }
+         c = ((c>>16) & 0xff) + ((c>>8) & 0xff) + (c & 0xff);
+         BM_UPUT(bm, x, ycorr(y), c > 3 * threshold * 255 ? 0 : 1);
        }
        TRY(bmp_pad(f));
    }
- break; case 0x320: /* 32-bit encoding with bitfields */
+ break; case 0x320: /* 32-bit encoding with bitfields */
    redshift = lbit(bmpinfo.RedMask);
    greenshift = lbit(bmpinfo.GreenMask);
    blueshift = lbit(bmpinfo.BlueMask);
}

```

(b) GPT-4o's patch.

```
==1010921==ERROR: AddressSanitizer: heap-buffer-overflow
on address 0x602000000030 at pc 0x0000004d74c0 bp 0
x7ffd06f11550 sp 0x7ffd06f11548
READ of size 8 at 0x602000000030 thread T0
#0 0x4d74bf in bmp_readbody_bmp src/bitmap_io.c:616:9
#1 0x4d205e in bmp_read src/bitmap_io.c:129:12
#2 0x4cb08d in process_file src/main.c:1056:9
#3 0x4c3f5d in main src/main.c:1212:7
#4 0x7fc5447afc86 in __libc_start_main (/lib/x86_64-
linux-gnu/libc.so.6+0x21c86)
#5 0x41b379 in _start (potrace+0x41b379)

0x602000000031 is located 0 bytes to the right of 1-byte
region [0x602000000030,0x602000000031)
allocated by thread T0 here:
#0 0x493abd in malloc (potrace+0x493abd)
#1 0x4dcd62 in bmp_new src/.bitmap.h:66:30
#2 0x4d53b8 in bmp_readbody_bmp src/bitmap_io.c:543:8
#3 0x4d205e in bmp_read src/bitmap_io.c:129:12
#4 0x4cb08d in process_file src/main.c:1056:9
#5 0x4c3f5d in main src/main.c:1212:7
#6 0x7fc5447afc86 in __libc_start_main (/lib/x86_64-
linux-gnu/libc.so.6+0x21c86)

SUMMARY: AddressSanitizer: heap-buffer-overflow src/
bitmap_io.c:616:9 in bmp_readbody_bmp

```

(c) AddressSanitizer log.

```
bitmap_io.c:376:14: runtime error: left shift of 255 by
24 places cannot be represented in type 'int'
#0 0x564053e35f3c in bmp_readint src/bitmap_io.c:376
#1 0x564053e362d7 in bmp_readbody_bmp src/bitmap_io.c
:465
#2 0x564053e3468b in bmp_read src/bitmap_io.c:129
#3 0x564053e32d4f in process_file src/main.c:1056
#4 0x564053e33a88 in main src/main.c:1212
#5 0x7fa0a20d6c86 in __libc_start_main (/lib/x86_64-
linux-gnu/libc.so.6+0x21c86)
#6 0x564053e2c489 in _start (src/potrace+0x2c489)

... (Omitted)

lzw.c:150:19: runtime error: left shift of 256 by 23
places cannot be represented in type 'int'
#0 0x564053e55e62 in lzw_emit src/lzw.c:150
#1 0x564053e5620d in lzw_encode_char src/lzw.c:183
#2 0x564053e56e11 in lzw_compress src/lzw.c:312
#3 0x564053e43e80 in lzw_xship src/flate.c:262
#4 0x564053e3a3bb in ship src/backend_eps.c:63
#5 0x564053e42818 in eps_init src/backend_eps.c:699
#6 0x564053e42a31 in page_eps src/backend_eps.c:738
#7 0x564053e332ca in process_file src/main.c:1113
#8 0x564053e33a88 in main src/main.c:1113

```

(d) UndefinedBehaviorSanitizer log.

Figure 10: (Top left) Developer's patch; (Top right) GPT-4o's patch; (Bottom left) AddressSanitizer log; (Bottom right) undefined behavior sanitizer log for CVE-2013-7437.

B.2 Solved by only GPT-4o case

CVE-2018-14498 The CVE-2018-14498 vulnerability was successfully patched only by GPT-4o. Figure 11a shows the developer patch, which added a conditional statement to check the length and prevent a buffer overflow. Figure 11b presents the patch generated by GPT-4o, where the model prevented buffer overflow by comparing the buffer size and len when reading the file.

```
diff --git a/cderror.h b/cderror.h
--- a/cderror.h
+++ b/cderror.h
@@ -49,6 +49,7 @@ JMESSAGE(JERR_BMP_NOT, "Not a BMP file - does not start with BM")
+JMESSAGE(JERR_BMP_OUTOFRANGE, "Numeric value out of range in BMP file")
+JMESSAGE(JTRC_BMP, "%ux%u 24-bit BMP image")
@@ -64,7 +64,7 @@ typedef struct _bmp_source_struct {
- int bits_per_pixel;
+ int bits_per_pixel;
+ int cmap_length;
} bmp_source_struct;
@@ -130,6 +130,8 @@ get_8bit_row (j_compress_ptr cinfo, cjpeg_source_ptr sinfo)
register JDIMENSION col;
+ int cmaplen = source->cmap_length;
+
/* Fetch next row from virtual array */
source->source_row--;
@@ -142,6 +144,8 @@ get_8bit_row (j_compress_ptr cinfo, cjpeg_source_ptr sinfo)
t = GETJSAMPLE(*inptr++);
+ if (t >= cmaplen)
+ ERREXIT(cinfo, JERR_BMP_OUTOFRANGE);
*outptr++ = colormap[0][t];
*outptr++ = colormap[1][t];
*outptr++ = colormap[2][t];
@@ -401,6 +405,7 @@ start_input_bmp (j_compress_ptr cinfo, cjpeg_source_ptr sinfo)
source->colormap = (*cinfo->mem->alloc_sarray)
((j_common_ptr) cinfo, JPOOL_IMAGE,
(JDIMENSION) biClrUsed, (JDIMENSION) 3);
+ source->cmap_length = (int)biClrUsed;
/* and read it from the file */
read_colormap(source, (int) biClrUsed, mapentrysize);
```

(a) Developer's patch.

```
diff --git a/rdbmp.c b/rdbmp.c
--- a/rdbmp.c
+++ b/rdbmp.c
@@ -45,9 +45,9 @@ typedef char U_CHAR;
-#define ReadOK(file,buffer,len) (JFREAD(file,buffer,len) == ((size_t) (len)))
+// FIXME: Crash CWE-125: Out-of-bounds Read
+ #define ReadOK(file,buffer,len) ((len) <= sizeof(buffer) && JFREAD(file,buffer,len) == ((size_t) (len)))
```

(b) GPT-4o's patch.

Figure 11: (Top) Developer's patch; (Bottom) GPT-4o's patch for CVE-2018-14498.

B.3 Claude Failure case

CVE-2012-513 Figure 12a shows the patch for CVE-2012-5134, where a check for `len > 0` was added to a conditional statement around line 4080 in the `xmlParseAttValueComplex` function. Figure 12b presents an unsuccessful patch by Claude 3.5 Sonnet. The problematic area was modified, but additional constraints were added, causing the patch to fail the functional test.

```
diff --git a/parser.c b/parser.c
--- a/parser.c
+++ b/parser.c
@@ -4076,7 +4076,7 @@ xmlParseAttValueComplex(
     xmlParserCtxtPtr ctxt, int *attlen, int
     normalize) {
     goto error;

     if ((in_space) && (normalize)) {
-       while (buf[len - 1] == 0x20) len--;
+       while ((len > 0) && (buf[len - 1] == 0x20))
+         len--;
     }
     buf[len] = 0;
     if (RAW == '<') {
```

(a) Developer's patch to address CVE-2012-5134.

```
diff --git a/parser.c b/parser.c
--- a/parser.c
+++ b/parser.c
@@ -4074,9 +4074,15 @@ xmlParseAttValueComplex(
     xmlParserCtxtPtr ctxt, int *attlen, int
     normalize) {
     }
     if (ctxt->instate == XML_PARSER_EOF)
         goto error;

-
+   if (len < 1 || buf == NULL) {
+       xmlFatalErrMsg(ctxt, XML_ERR_INTERNAL_ERROR,
+           "Invalid buffer or length in
+           attribute value\n");
+       goto error;
+   }

     if ((in_space) && (normalize)) {
-       while (buf[len - 1] == 0x20) len--;
+       while (len > 0 && buf[len - 1] == 0x20) len
+         --;
     }
     buf[len] = 0;
     if (RAW == '<') {
```

(b) Claude 3.5 Sonnet's unsuccessful patch to address CVE-2012-5134.

Figure 12: (Left) Developer's patch; (Right) Claude 3.5 Sonnet's unsuccessful patch for CVE-2012-5134.

C Prompt and Code Context Example

In this section, we present the prompts and code context used in SAN2PATCH, illustrated with a real example of patching CVE-2016-1839 using GPT-4o. Each of the four stages – *Vulnerability Comprehension*, *Where-To-Fix*, *How-To-Fix*, and *Candidate Generation* — is summarized with corresponding figures. Due to page limitations, we omit multiple responses generated for each prompt. In the prompts, **blue text** highlights values passed from previous stages or user input, while **green text** indicates where the code context is inserted.

Figure 13: *Vulnerability Comprehension* branching prompts. Note that we used CoT-SC in this stage, repeating the prompt K times and aggregating the K responses into one result.

Figure 14: *Vulnerability Comprehension* aggregation prompt. Each `<Vulnerability_Comprehension_i>` represents the output of the branching prompt described in 13.

Figure 15: *Where-To-Fix* prompts. In this stage, we use ToT prompting to generate K independent results, each of which is scored separately; pruning is then performed based on the scores using greedy or sampling methods, without LLM.

Figure 16: *How-To-Fix* prompts. The prompting method in this stage is the same as that used in *Where-To-Fix*.

Figure 17: Candidate Generation prompts. K patch candidates are generated, but scoring and pruning are skipped; instead, Patch Validation is performed directly.